

CHRISTIAN FAITH AS A VALUE IN RECOVERING DRUG ADDICTS

Anca-Georgiana DRĂGAN-MOLDOVEANU

University of Bucharest, Faculty of Sociology and Social Work

Master's Degree Graduate

anca.dragan@s.unibuc.ro

Assoc. Prof. Emanuel Adrian SÂRBU, PhD, PhD Habil

University of Bucharest, Faculty of Baptist Theology

Doctoral School of Theology and Religious Studies

esarbu@ftb.unibuc.ro

ABSTRACT: Christian Faith as a Value in Recovering Drug Addicts.

Over the years, the problem of drug consumption led the discussions in two major directions, namely the prevention strategies and intervention methods. For an intervention method to be effective, it must have a holistic approach that includes the physical, emotional, socio-professional, and spiritual side of the addict. This is necessary because when a drug user reaches the point to experience addiction, this affects all aspects of his life: his beliefs, his values, and eventually, his behaviors. Behaviors such as lying, manipulating, stealing, are very specific to someone who would do anything to have money for the next dose. Therefore, in the recovering process of an addict, a new change of his personal values plays an important role. He needs to learn new, healthy behaviors, and Christian values can be a solid foundation for this.

Keywords: *drugs; addiction; recovering process; values; Christian values; holistic approach.*

1. A short overview on the drugs addiction and its effects

Over the last decades, the modern society has encountered very complex and difficult to manage problems, drug consumption being among those with increasingly worrying consequences. Unfortunately, our country was not spared from this phenomenon. A real reason for our concern is the per-

centages attested by the national reports regarding the number of people who have tried an illicit drug at least once. According to a recent study carried out in 2019 by the National Antidrug Agency, for a general population estimated at 19,37 million of inhabitants, the prevalence of the consumption of any type of illicit drug is 11,9%¹.

An analysis of the data above shows that more than two million people have tried a type of illicit drug at least once in their lifetime in our country. Now, the number is probably even higher. Many of these people will not only remain at the stage of having tried the drug only once, but they will continue to use it long term and even end up experiencing addiction.

Very often, the dramas caused by the pain of drug consumption and addiction remain hidden by this families, as a desperate attempt to avoid stigma and emotional pain. Many parents experience deep feelings of guilt and shame, believing that the behavior of their child is often a direct reflection of how they were raised and a result of their quality in parenting. Even if, in the recent years, the perception and social reactions towards drug users express a greater amount of sensitivity and compassion, there are still people who label them as immoral, irredeemable, or worthless. Often, drug users take on this identity, especially after experiencing multiple relapses in their attempt to quit.

The same, or sometimes even harder, is the drama of the Christian families who are facing addiction problems. For many Christians, drug consumption is still a taboo subject because of it being considered a sinful and undesirable behavior. However, as previous research shown, substance use is not absent among Christian believers². Since Romania is a highly religious country³, faith and aspects related to faith are probably more relevant than in other countries, with a larger proportion of secularized people. Many churches here tend to express an attitude of denial towards the possibility of the existence of this problem in the community. This attitude discourages those who are struggling with addiction from asking

1 Agenția Națională Antidrog, *Raportul Național privind situația drogurilor în România*, București, 2020, p.30.

2 E. A. Sârbu, O.i. Bunaciu, D. Mariș (eds), *The Substance Use and Social Factors in Bucharest 2012-2013*, Cluj-Napoca, Editura Risoprint, 2014, pp. 60-86.

3 E.A., Sârbu, F. Lazăr, A.F. Popovici, A.F. *Individual, Familial and Social Environment Factors Associated with Religiosity Among Urban High School Students*. *Rev Relig Res* (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13644-021-00466-x>.

for help, and also affecting the ones in relapse of drug use after a period of abstinence⁴. Often, this happens because some of the consequences of this behavior, such as lying, manipulation, theft, sexual relationships, and violence are antagonistic to all the values that Christianity promotes. As a result, the drug user is considered a sinner and his addiction a consequence of moving away from God.

Still, the need for the involvement of Christian churches in helping addicts is essential, both as a practical form of manifesting Christ's love for those who do not know God, but also as a response to the increasing rate of drug use even amongst the youth in our local churches. Drugs don't play any favorites because both the people from inside and outside the Christian churches consume it in different percentages. It is one of the reasons why the discussions about drugs addiction have always tried to identify the source of this problem.

As it was already mentioned above, over the years, this phenomenon has gained momentum, and there have been various ways in which the problem has been approached, among them: addiction as *a disease* - which leads to the need for rehabilitation, addiction as *a problem of choice* - which leads to the need of coercive measures, or addiction as *a sin* - which leads to the idea of liberating the addict from the bondage of addiction with the help of God⁵. In this context, some discussion may be: "Is the addict a sick or sinful person?"; "Can a drug addict still be held accountable for his addiction?"; "Does a drug addict still have autonomy?" To reach the most relevant answers, we need to understand both what drugs are and what addiction is.

The World Health Organization defines the drug as "the substance which, once absorbed by the living organism, can modify one or more of its functions"⁶. A synthesis of the effects of drugs consumption is presented by Gilles Ferreol, who classifies them into *expected* and *undesirable*. Among

4 Anca-Georgiana Drăgan-Moldoveanu, Emanuel Adrian SÂRBU, „Recăderea în consumul de droguri - rolul comunităților terapeutice în activitățile de prevenire [Relapse to Drug Use – the Role of Therapeutic Communities in Prevention Activities]”, *Revista de Asistență Socială*, Issue 2/ 2021, București, http://www.swreview.ro/index.pl/relapse_to_drug_use_the_role_of_therapeutic_communities_in_prevention_activities.

5 Sjaak Monster, *Process of change and the treatment plan*, Bucharest, 2019, pp. 22-24;

6 Gabriela Trifan, Radu Năforniță, *Consumul și traficul de droguri- practici de specialitate în domeniul prevenirii și combaterii consumului și traficului de droguri*, București, Pro Universitaria 2016: 9;

the *expected* effects we find joy, psychological excitement, calmness or even changes in perception, and as *undesirable* he lists addiction and negative effects on the brain, heart, or other human vital organs⁷.

In the first phase, the drug users have a very positive perception of the changes in their condition. Very often they describe effects such as euphoria, a sense of peace, and a sense of escaping from the current reality. But everything changes when they begin to feel the pain of the consequences of their consumption. That first feeling of an immense satisfaction is absorbed by the problems of becoming addicted to the substance.

Addiction is one of the consequences of a long-term consumption. Some of the characteristics of an addict are: a great fear of pain that he is trying to escape by using drugs, his craving for immediate gratification and living for the immediate moment⁸. Therefore, to understand addiction, one must first understand the stages that the drug user goes through before he becomes an addict.

A proposal comes from the authors of the book *Basic Concepts on Drug Use Disorders*, respectively: (1) *Initiation of consumption* - when after the first contact with the drug, the user develops a mostly positive attitude towards it; (2) *The development of an addicted behavior* - when the negative reinforced process also appears, and the user ends up administering the drug to cope with the unpleasant state he feels after giving up consumption; (3) *Cessation* - is when the individual decides to stop using, and even recovers some of the normal behaviors, but the medicine considers that he is left with a predisposition to use because his neural systems have adapted to new behavioral changes; (4) *Facing relapses* - when various circumstances can lead back to consumption even after period of abstinence that can reach several years⁹.

As a conclusion, a behavior becomes addictive when: (1) is the result of a pattern that becomes, over time, a habit, (2) it gets stronger as you practice it, (3) involves short term thinking which seeks immediate pleasure to cope with distress or discomfort and to make the person with

7 Gilles Ferreol, 2000 apud. Mariana Bălan, „Efectele Economice și sociale ale consumului de droguri în context european”, *Acta Universitatis George Bacovia. Juridica*, Bacău, 2019, vol. 8, nr.1, p. 5;

8 David Batty, *Understanding the steps to relapse*, Global Teen Challenge, 2013, p. 32;

9 Gabriel Cicu et. al, *Concepte de bază privind tulburările datorate consumului de droguri*, București, Detectiv, 2007, pp. 30-31.

such behaviors feel normal, and (4) in the long term, it incurs costs such as problems and relationships, financial difficulties and others¹⁰. This is usually the moment when the drug user begins to see the self-destructive consequences of his behavior and the positive effects provided by the substance are diminishing.

Although drug addiction can be analyzed through its physical effects, nevertheless, the fact that many drug users continue to use the substance despite the consequences, and when the physical need no longer explains it, leads to the need to approach addiction from both a physical and psychological perspective. *Physical addiction* is manifested by the addict's tendency to maintain sufficient levels of drug(s) in the body, both to benefit from the pleasure provided by the drug and to prevent the discomfort and physical pain caused by withdrawal¹¹. Conversely, *psychological addiction* is motivated exclusively by the hedonic effects experienced after using a drug. These are related to the action of drugs on the cerebral reward nervous system, which leads to the release of hormones such as dopamine, which manifests the role of regulating affective states¹².

In the long term, drug addiction produces very serious effects, such as: *physical effects* (losing weight, health problems, withdrawal symptoms), *psychological effects* (memory disorders, attention disorders, panic, low self-esteem, suicide attempts), *social effects* (marginalization, social exclusion, aggression, lack of interest in work and school), *economic effects* (poverty, vagrancy, medical costs, and the costs for the recovery)¹³.

As Christians, we also see the spiritual effects that drugs have on the user: conscious lying, manipulation, or other sinful behaviors, irregular attendance to churches programs, and as a result, alienation from God. Often, addicts end up blaming God for their sad context and even denying Him because He allowed it. Questions like: "If He exists, why did He allow this suffering in my life?"; "Why doesn't He intervene?"; "Why doesn't He set me free instantly from my addiction?" often appear.

10 Smart Recovery, *Instrumente și strategii pentru a te ajuta în călătoria spre recuperare*, ediția a 3-a, 2013, publicat de către Alcohol & Drugs Abuse Self-Help Network: 93;

11 Denis Richard, Jean-Louis Senon, *Dicționar de droguri, toxicomanii și dependențe*, Editura Științelor Medicale, București, 1999, p. 504.

12 Idem, p.6;

13 Mariana Bălan, *Efectele Economice și sociale ale consumului de droguri în context european*, Acta Universitatis George Bacovia. Juridica, Bacău, 2019, pp. 4-6.

2. The need for a holistic approach in the process of recovery from addiction

SAMSHA defines recovery as "a process of change through which individuals improve their health and well-being and learn to live independent lives and strive to reach their full potential"¹⁴. Recovery involves a profound transformation of people, through a process in which they are often taught to build their lives from scratch, starting from the smallest habits. The road to a new life is not easy, because many of their behaviors are reinforced in mindsets formed over many years.

Dave Batty suggests four phases of recovery: (1) *Intervention* - when the addict family is usually taught how to stop enabling the person with a problem and how not to offer the wrong kind of help; (2) *Detox* - which helps the person beyond the major physical sickness because of withdrawing; (3) *Learning steps to healthy living* - by resolving the traumas from the past, rebuilding healthy relationship, and, as a Christian, by learning how to live in God's truth; (4) *Transition back to society* - when it becomes normal to have a healthy living¹⁵.

So, detoxification is not enough for the recovery of an addict, but he needs a context where to learn to live a healthy and normal life. This process involves the change of certain beliefs and, as a result, of his personal values. Values are the basis of the human decision-making process¹⁶. Values determine a person's behavior and influence their choices. In this sense, a suitable context is needed, where the addict acquires new beliefs.

One such type of services offered to drug users is therapeutic communities, with long term residential programs. A definition of the therapeutic communities is attributed to the European Federation of Therapeutic Communities, in 1991: a drug-free environment in which various people who suffered deficiencies in all the areas of their lives, due to consumption, learn to live in a healthy environment, based on rules and structure, and which help them to return to society as functional persons¹⁷.

14 SAMSHA, *SAMSHA's working definition on recovery. 10 principles of recovery*. PEP 12- RECDEF- First Printed 2012, p.3.

15 David Batty, *Understanding the steps to relapse*, Global Teen Challenge, 2013, pp. 36-45.

16 Richard Barret *The Importance of Values in Building a High-Performance Culture*. Barret Values Center, p.1.

17 Ottenberg, 1993, pp. 51-52 *apud* Gabriela Trifan, Radu Năforință, *Consumul și traficul de droguri - practici de specialitate în domeniul prevenirii și combaterii consumului și traficului de droguri*, București, Pro Universitaria, 2016, p. 93.

The role of the therapeutic community is not only to offer a shelter, but to create a safe place, even a family atmosphere, where the addicts feel accepted and supported. The successful combination is the result of the clear structure, the interpersonal relationship, but also the various activities through which the residents are helped to develop new skills and to equip themselves for the moment when they return to the real life.

As a conclusion, recovering from addiction needs a holistic approach. Therapeutic communities are based on forms of therapy that support each resident towards physical, emotional, socio-professional, and spiritual recovery. The program structure, the daily activities aim at recovery: *physical* (through sports, routine, healthy meals), *emotional* (through individual and group therapy), *socio-professional* (thorough occupational therapy, self-management, developing new skills), and *spiritual* (by developing an authentic relationship with God which creates a sense of purpose and fulfillment on a deep level)¹⁸.

3. The spiritual dimension of addiction

Many would wonder what the connection between God and drug addiction is. A quote attributed to Blaise Pascale says: "In the heart of every man there is a void in the form of God, which cannot be filled by any created thing, but only by God, our Creator".

Drug users often justify their debut in consumption because of a need to fulfill a void to which they tried to provide various surrogates like relationships, material possessions, drug use, but which ultimately proved to be unfillable. Every person is born with a need for purpose, and the things by which they try to fulfill this intrinsic need turn out to be illusory in the end. Most of the times, these surrogates leave them with even a higher state of emptiness, when the effect stops.

Understanding this need, more and more intervention methods that are based on a Christian philosophy and principles started their activity, and their effectiveness in recovery has been demonstrated over the years.

One of the most well-known programs for the recovery of addicts is *The 12 steps program* initiated by Alcoholics Anonymous. The AA group was originally established in a Christian context, but over the years it has

18 Teen Challenge Romania, <https://www.teenchallenge.ro/modelul-tc/>. Accesed 26.07.2022. 21:18;

re-adapted its approach to offer accessibility to believers of other religions and atheists. Today, AA and NA are among the most well-known and successful therapeutic models that support drug addicts¹⁹.

Also, from the second half of the 20th century more and more Christian communities began to get involved in the support of addicted people. This eventually led to the emergence of Christian therapeutic communities, which have as their foundation and approach in the philosophy of recovery, the Christians principles. Communities that are based on the Christian faith address the medical and spiritual needs of the drug addict, with a special focus on the spiritual element, associated with traditional addiction recovery techniques such as: detoxification, individual and group therapy, cognitive behavioral therapy, learning new skills, and emotional preparation to face real-life changes. Communities of this kind allow addicts to include worship as part of their recovery plan, and provide spaces for prayer, Scripture (Bible) reading, religious services, or any other discussions common to faith-based rehabilitation²⁰.

Another therapeutic community with a recovery program based on Christian principles is the Teen Challenge program, which lasts one year, offering 24/7 support. The holistic approach is the key to recovery of this program, and the system of beliefs and values of Teen Challenge organization also includes the conviction that when a drug addict makes a sincere decision to embrace faith in Jesus Christ, and he will constantly apply His principles in the daily routine, he will benefit from a spiritual experience that will change his life and help him stay sober. So, the difference between a traditional rehabilitation program and Teen Challenge is the focus on Jesus Christ, called the *Jesus Factor*. The environment based on a Christian faith, the daily devotional time and Bible studies facilitate healing, and lead the residents to a new life. Over the years, studies have shown that the number one reason people stay sober after the program is completed is their genuine faith in God²¹.

19 Rhondaa G. Burnet, *Faith based programs in the treatment of substance*, B.S., Southern Illinois University, 2008, pp.1-2.

20 Addiction Center, <https://www.addictioncenter.com/treatment/faith-based-drug-and-alcohol-rehab/>. Accessed 23.07.2022, ora 21:28;

21 Teen Challenge USA, *Adults and Teen Challenge, Our Program*, <https://teenchallengeusa.org/about>. Accessed 24.07.2022, 10:58;

4. Christian faith as a value in recovering drugs addicts

The Teen Challenge organization has been active since 1958, having over 65 years of experience in working with addicts.

In Romania, the organization has been operating since 2003, and it currently has three residential centers, two for men and one for women. Since then, hundreds of residents have been in the program, and many of them are now responsible people making a difference in society. The program is very intensive and with very clear objectives. Residents are initiated and made responsible starting from the smallest habits such as rhythm of life, punctuality, cooking, etc., to the most complex human aspect like self-knowledge, emotional intelligence, altruism, etc.²². Statistics released in 2020 for the period 2008-2020 at the men center show a success rate of 89,2% among the program graduates²³.

For a deeper understanding of the impact and effectiveness of the Teen Challenge approach, a study was carried out on two of the centers - the one addressed to women and the other addressed to men.

Methodology

The research was conducted through both a quantitative and a qualitative study. The quantitative study was carried out based on a questionnaire, applied to 74 respondents. The qualitative study was carried out based on the semi-structured interview, with two categories of respondents. The first interview was applied to 15 members of the Teen Challenge Team, from the two centers, including the Executive Director. The second interview was applied to a number of 12 members of the residents' families.

Sampling: The sample consist of a total number of 101 respondents, of which 74 in the questionnaire, 15 in the interview addressed to the staff-members, and 12 in the interview addressed to the resident's family members.

For the questionnaire answers to be considered relevant, the questionnaire was applied to some of the residents who have experienced at least three months in the program in one of the two centers. The respondents were both female and male, and they have experienced addiction prior to the program.

22 Teen Challenge Romania, *Descriere generală Teen Challenge România*, 2021: 1;

23 Teen Challenge Romania, *Statistici realizate la centrul de băieți Grădiștea*, 2020;

For the interview addressed to the staff, the sample consists of a number of 15 respondents, six women who are working at the women center and eight men who are working at the men center, plus the Executive Director. Each of the respondents must have a period of at least six months of being part of the team.

For the interview addressed to the family members, the sample consists of a number of 12 female respondents, who have different roles in the relationship with the residents, and their family members have stayed at least three months in the program.

To carry out the research, the unit of analysis is represented by minors and adults who have a direct or indirect role in the Teen Challenge Romania community. The subject of the analysis refers to the importance of the therapeutic community in the holistic restoration of an addict, and the relationships that have been affected by addiction, starting from the perspective of some essential categories like residents, staff members and relatives.

Hypotheses and research question: One of the *hypotheses* and the *research question* aimed to understand if there is a defining element in the successful recovery through the Teen Challenge program.

Objectives: To achieve the purpose of this research, the following objectives were established:

The *general objective* was to study the effectiveness of the therapeutic community for addicted people starting from the management model of the Teen Challenge Romania organization, from the perspective of the residents, the employed staff members, and the family members. Also, one of the *specific objectives* was to identify the main element that, from the perspective of residents, staff members and family members, determines the increased success rate of the program.

The limitation of the research

A limitation that was encountered is the fact that some of the residents who were in the program, were unable to approach due to the lack of contact information, and among those to whom the questionnaire was sent, not all of them wanted to answer the questions. Another limitation is related to the family member respondents, since the number who answered is not very high, and data could be influenced if the number would increase.

Research results

Some of the most important conclusions of the research will be outlined below.

1. Acquiring new personal values and behaviors.

Above was already mentioned that the process of recovery involves changing certain beliefs, which will eventually lead to the change of some personal values.

When the residents were asked to mention their behaviors in the period when they were using drugs, 65 of 74 mention they were lying, 64 mention manipulation, 51 mention the sale of some personal things, 47 mention theft, and 39 mention aggressivity. To change these destructive behaviors, it was necessary to acquire new values.

The main values of the organization are discipleship, excellence, unity, competence, hospitality, compassion, forgiveness, clarity, and others. The most important is discipleship. Discipleship is the process by which the residents are helped to give up old and destructive mentalities and mechanisms to survive, and to acquire new mentalities, beliefs, values, and principles. These new values will help them to have integrity, that will reflect in their small and big choices, but also in their everyday behaviors. Another expression by which discipleship is understood is that it teaches the residents to behave in a manner worthy of God. This means being honest, taking responsibility for their actions and giving up any sinful behavior, such as lying, cheating, theft etc, which will be replaced with a healthy one.

The Teen Challenge program is based on Christian principles and values. A conclusion of the research is that the organization values are known by the staff members, who have appropriated them, and based on which they make decisions and behave. The residents recognize the organization's values and directly benefit from them, especially the discipleship process that helps them build a whole new character. Also, these values are observed by the family of the residents when they see their new behavior at home.

Already during the program, the family members see the changes in the residents' behavior, starting from the smallest habits at home such as they make their beds, clean the house, and help with shopping, to the deepest aspects of their personal values like the fact that they keep calm in

communication, they have patience, they stop swearing, they don't lie, and they start assuming their role in the family. From damaged and abusive relationships, where the family members were manipulated for money, and a total absence of involvement of the addicts in the household chores, now, because of the new values acquired during the program, their behavior is changed to a responsible one.

2. Setting long-term objectives.

Another conclusion of the study is related to the accomplishment of the three objectives of the Teen Challenge program. The residents are now aware that giving up drugs is not enough if they don't experience a deep level of transformation. Otherwise, this can turn into a context abstinence. The program objectives aim for profound transformation, and the residents understand the long-term importance in developing integrity, increased work capacity, and increased frustration tolerance by addressing conflicts assertively. This will help them not to experience relapse when they go back home, and they face the pressure of the real life. Christian faith and values help them better manage their emotions and understand the importance of making no compromise.

These three objectives are:

- a) *To acquire a genuine faith:* This may lead to speculation that the hidden objective is to change their religion. But this is not true. The real objective is to help them achieve strong beliefs, which will influence their daily behaviors, and will generate sincerity, integrity, and commitment.
- b) *Increasing their capacity for work and standards,* which is based on the vision to help them understand the importance of working with excellence. A hardworking individual with standards of excellence will have many opportunities. To help them and to teach them in this process, each project completed by a resident is carefully checked by the staff members. Anything that can be improved is shown to him and he is taught how to do it better next time.
- c) *To acquire skills to deal with difficult people and situation* aims to approach conflicts assertively. Low tolerance to frustration can easily lead to relapse. However, conflicts are a normal part of life and cannot be avoided, but they can be managed healthy.

Residents know the objectives of the program. 66 of 74 respondents chose to *acquire a genuine faith* as the first objective, 54 of 74 chose as to *acquire skills to deal with difficult people and situation* the second objective, 46 of 74 chose *raising my capacity to work and standards* as the third objective. The answers were motivated by the fact that *"accomplishing these three objectives decreases the chance of relapse"*, that *"the three objectives lead to a strong character"* or the fact that *"a lack of these skills and conviction led to wrong decisions in the past"*.

3. The defining element in the success recovery through Teen Challenge program

First, the residents were asked what their religious beliefs were before coming in the program. 31 of 74 answered they were non-practicing believers, 13 declared themselves atheists, 17 used to attend church only for special events, and the others had different beliefs.

Although the residents mentioned various fears towards the religious component of the program, such as the fact that they would be brainwashed, that they would end up in a sect or, many of them did not even understand the connection between God and drug addiction, yet when they were asked to mention the Christian faith in their recovery they chose: 53 of 74 said it radically changed their beliefs, 49 said that from hopeless persons they become givers of hope, 46 said it helped them to have integrity, 43 said they feel that now they have a purpose, 39 said their sense of worth increased, and 35 said that now they experience fulfillment on a deep level.

At the end, the question *"If you would have to choose the most important element that contributes to the success of the residents what would it be?"*, was addressed to all the three categories of respondents. 48 of 74 respondents from the residents chose the faith in God and the Christian values, 15 of 15 respondents from the staff members chose the faith in God and the Christian values and 9 of 12 respondents from the family members chose the same.

When the residents were asked to motivate the previous answers, they highlighted aspects such as *"the strength God gave them in the hardest moments, the sense of peace"*, the changes in the behavior like, now *"I forgive easier and I am a free person"*, the feeling that *"the void in their soul is now fulfilled"*, but also the fact that many of them have experienced other forms of therapy previously like psychologists, detox hospitals, and yet they did not succeed until they came to Teen Challenge, a Christian program.

Also, the answer to another direct question: "*What do you think is the role of God and the Christian values in the process of recovery?*", addressed to the residents, reflect that 65 of 74 said it is *the most important*.

The staff members motivated their choice by the fact that only God can produce a deep transformation, and a person cannot change another person. Then, a transformed person begins to have peace, joy, and to become a testimony in society and at home. These people change their values, principles, and have a new life.

Also, the 9 respondents among the family members which declared their faith in God and Christian values as the defining element motivated their answer by the fact that now the resident who experienced the program has radically changed his life mentality, values, and found a real purpose in life.

A conclusion concerns the defining element in the success recovery through the Teen Challenge program, according to the results of this research, shows that the key to success may be considered the faith in God and acquiring of the Christian values.

After finishing the program, most of the residents continue to promote the Christian values and in a very practical way, to transform these values into healthy behaviors. A potential discussion question would be if the addiction to substances, or habits has now been replaced by an addiction to God. To an extent, it can be considered so, especially since it becomes part of the daily life. At the same time, if we analyze the consequences of addiction to substance and habits, compared to the impact of Christian values, we can see how harmful the former is compared to the latter.

The recovery of an addict lead to the restoration of his entire family. He becomes a functional, active socio-professional person with a normal life. Many of them are even actively involved in prevention campaigns of in helping other addicts. Therefore, increasing the number of communities that help addicts becomes a must in the current situation of our country regarding drug consumption.

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